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**THE CURRENT STATE OF THE PROBLEM OF RECONSTRUCTIVE
AND RESTORATIVE OPERATIONS FOR COLONIC STOMA****Mamadiev A.M.¹****Aliboev M.R.²**¹⁻²Andijan State Medical Institute Andijan, Uzbekistan<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7336788>

Currently, The Trend Towards A Steady Increase In Tumor Diseases Of The Large Intestine Continues Throughout The World, Which Is Associated With Improved Diagnosis And Increased Oncological Alertness Of The Population.

Purpose Of The Study. To Improve The Method Of Forming A Combined Stoma With Colo-Colonostomy In Case Of Left-Sided Acute Obstruction Of The Large Intestine Of Tumor And Non-Tumor Genesis

Materials And Methods Were 96 Patients Who For The Period From 2011 To 2020. In The Andijan Branch Of The Republican Scientific Center For Emergency Medical Care, Various Surgical Interventions Were Performed On The Large Intestine For Acute Obstruction Of The Large Intestine Of Tumor And Non-Tumor Genesis

According To Recent Decades Of Research In The Surgical Treatment Of Acute Obstruction Of The Large Intestine Of Tumor And Non-Tumor Origin, Many Issues In Determining Surgical Tactics Remain Complex And Debatable. There Is Also A Lack Of Unity Of Views On The Radical Nature Of The Operation In Acute Intestinal Obstruction Of Non-Tumor Genesis, As Well As In The Tumor Nature Of The Disease. A Number Of Surgeons Explain This Situation With Great Opportunities For Choice. Nevertheless, During Surgical Interventions, One Should Strive To Solve Two Main Tasks: A) To Decompress The Intestine; B) Resect The Area Of The Intestine That Carries The Tumor. A Number Of Researchers Note That Surgical Treatment Of Acute Obstruction Of The Large Intestine With The Formation Of A Colonic Stoma In The Long Term Does Not Significantly Prolong Life, Leading To High Mortality (43-47.5%). In Addition, The Frequency Of Postoperative Complications Compared With One-Stage Operations Does Not Have A Significant Difference.

In Connection With The Development Of Medical Science And Technology In Recent Years, Individual Reports Of Surgeons On The Use Of Laparoscopic Operations On The Colon Began To Appear. So, Stoyko Yu.M. Et Al. Presented The Experience Of Performing Laparoscopic Reconstructive Surgery After The Hartmann Operation In 23 Patients. The Median Duration Of The Operation Was 180 Minutes. (From 105 To 370 Min.). The Conversion Rate Is 4.3%, Anastomotic Failure Is 4.3%, And Postoperative Complications Are 13%. Taking Into Account The Initial Fundamental Complexity Of Reconstructive And Restorative Operations, Laparoscopic Access For Such Interventions Should Be Justified. The Selection Of Patients For Laparoscopic Surgery Should Be Based On

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Criteria That Reduce The Risk Of Failure Of The Laparoscopic Approach. It Should Be Noted That Laparoscopic Surgical Interventions Are Just Beginning To Be Introduced Into Clinical Practice And Only A Few Specialized Clinics Own These Technologies.

Conclusion. Thus, Acute Obstruction Of The Large Intestine Of Tumor Genesis Remains Extremely Relevant, Due To A Number Of Unresolved Issues In Determining Surgical Tactics And Surgical Rehabilitation Of Colostomy Patients. In Particular, There Is A High Incidence Of Postoperative Complications And Mortality, As Well As Persistent Disability In Patients With Colostomy.